

γ, γ -Disubstituted Itaconic Acids. Part VII.¹ The Stobbe Condensation of Benzyl-, *p*-Chlorobenzyl-, and *p*-Methoxybenzylphenyl Ketones with Diethyl Succinate

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Cis (Ph/Ar)-5-Aryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoic acids were converted into ethyl *trans*-(Ph/Ar)-5-aryl-3-carboxy-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoate (14), (15) and (16), which have been cyclised to 1-acetoxy-naphthalenes (17), (18) and (19).

Cis (Ph/Ar)-4, 5-Diphenyl- and *cis* (Ph/Ar)-4-phenyl-5-*p*-tolyl-pent-4-enoic acid anhydrides were converted with aluminium chloride to a mixture of the corresponding cyclopentenones and arylidene tetralone carboxylic acids. *Trans* (Ph/CO₂Et)-5-Aryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-phenyl-pent-3-enoic acids were cyclised to ethyl 4-acetoxy-1-arylmethyl-2-naphthoates.

BENZYL, *p*-chlorobenzyl and *p*-methoxybenzyl phenyl ketones were condensed with diethyl succinate in the presence of potassium *t*-butoxide² to give a mixture of half-esters from which *cis* (Ph/Ar)-5-aryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoic acids (1), (2) and (3) were isolated as crystalline solids. The remaining oil (fraction B) proved to contain a mixture of the former half esters and a small amount of the isomeric *trans* (Ph'CO₂Et) - 5 -aryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-phenyl-pent-3-enoic acids (4), (5) and (6), respectively. However, a small amount of (5) was also isolated in a crystalline form.

Establishment of the Position of the Double Bond in the Crystalline Half-esters (1, 2, 3 and 5). This was inferred from their i.r. spectra (Table 1) and definitely established by ozonolysis. Thus, ozonolysis of (1), (2) and (3) gave β -benzoylpropionic acid together with the corresponding aromatic aldehyde, whereas (5) gave *p*-chlorobenzyl phenyl ketone.

Estimation of the Ratio of the Isomeric Half-esters in the Oily Fractions (B).—From the weight of β -benzoylpropionic acid and arylmethyl phenyl ketones obtained on ozonolysis of fraction (B), the amounts of (1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6) in the oily fractions (B) were determined.

The composition of (B) obtained in case of *p*-chlorobenzyl phenyl ketone was also estimated by u.v. spectroscopy³ (cf. experimental), the result of which was in good agreement with that obtained by ozonolysis.

Taking into consideration the composition of (B), the overall ratio of (1, 2 and 3) to (4, 5 and 6) is about 4:1 (cf. Table 2), respectively.

The considerable predominance of half-esters (1, 2 and 3) over the isomeric half-esters (4, 5 and 6) is expected in view of the more stability conferred upon the molecule by the extended conjugation involving the two aryl groups.

TABLE 1—5-ARYL-3-ETHOXYCARBONYL-4-PHENYL-PENT-4-AND PENT-3-ENOIC ACIDS

Compound	M. P. (°C)	Found			Formula	Required%			ν C=O/cm ⁻¹
		C	H	Cl		C	H	Cl	
(1)	92.3	74.5	6.5		C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄	74.1	6.2		1695, # 1724 Δ
(2)	104	67.0	5.5	9.7	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClO ₄	66.9	5.3	9.9	1695, # 1724 Δ
(3)	116-7	70.6	6.3		C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₆	71.2	6.3		1695, # 1709 Δ
(5)	140	67.1	5.5	9.8	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClO ₄	66.9	5.3	9.9	1700, # 1718 Δ Δ
(6)	137	70.7	6.15		C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₆	71.2	6.3		1700, # 1718 Δ Δ

of aliphatic acids.^{11(a)}

Δ of esters^{11(b)}

Δ Δ of α, β -unsaturated esters.^{11(b)}

TABLE 2—RATIO OF PENT-4-ENOIC TO PENT-3-ENOIC ACIDS IN THE STOBBE PRODUCTS

Compound	Wt. (g) of crude product	Wt. (g) of crystalline half-ester	Wt. (g) of oily fraction of half-esters	Wt. (g) of each component in oil fraction	Total (g)	Ratio of Δ^4 to Δ^3 pentenoic acids
(1)	82.4	42.4	40	21.8	64.2	4.4 : 1
(4)		—		14.5	14.5	
(2)	33.5	23.0	8.0	4.0	27.0	4.5 : 1
(5)		2.5		3.4	5.9	
(3)	27.2	14.0	13.2	7.85	21.85	5 : 1
(6)		—		4.3	4.3	

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TABLE 3—*cis* (PH/AR)-5-ARYL-3-CARBOXY 4-PHENYL-PENT-4-ENOIC ACIDS

Compound	M. P. (°C)	Found			Formula	Required%			$\nu_{\text{C=O}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$
		C	H	Cl		C	H	Cl	
(8)	153 ⁺	72.7	5.3		C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄	73.0	5.4		1701
(9)	170 [‡]	65.4	4.7	10.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClO ₄	65.35	4.6	10.7	1704
(10)	152 Δ	70.0	5.7		C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₅	69.9	5.6		1701

+from benzene-ether, lit.¹² m.p. 151.2-152°. ‡from toluene-light petroleum
 Δ from benzene-light petroleum * of saturated aliphatic acids.^{11(a)}

Attempted cyclisation of (1), (2) and (3) was unsuccessful. This may be due to the fact that the most stable conformation around the C₂-C₃ σ -bond is that in which the stilbene residue (designated as G) and the CO₂H are staggered as in (7). Such conformation is not favourable for cyclisation. It may also be attributed to the failure of these half-esters to isomerise under the reaction conditions to *trans* (Ph/CO₂Et) half-esters (4), (5) and (6), which are easily cyclised to the corresponding naphthalene derivatives (*inter alia*).

Saponification of (1), (2) and (3) gave the dibasic acids (8), (9) and (10) respectively, with no migration of the double bond, since on ozonolysis they gave β -benzoyl-propionic acid and the corresponding aromatic aldehydes. These dibasic acids were converted into the corresponding anhydrides (11), (12) and (13) (viscous oils), which on ethanolysis gave ethyl *trans* (Ph/Ar)-5-aryl-3-carboxy-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoates (14, 15 and 16 respectively).

Stereochemical Configuration of the Isomeric Half-esters derived from Pent-4-enoic Acids—This was established by a study of the n.m.r. spectra of (1) and (14). The coupling constants (J) for the CH multiplet in the spectrum of (1) is ca. 5.0 cps whereas that in (14) is ca. 7-9 cps. This indicates that the two compounds should have different geometrical configurations, compound (14), with the higher coupling constant is most probably the *trans*-isomer^{4a}. To establish at

which step in the conversion of (1) into (14) isomerisation takes place, the n.m.r. spectrum of the dibasic acid (8) was determined. The J value for the multiplet of the CH proton is found to range from 3-4 cps, which indicates that the dibasic acid most probably has the *cis*-configuration. Saponification of the anhydride (11) under mild conditions gave the dibasic acid (8), which indicates that no isomerisation appears to take place during anhydride formation.

The isomerisation, therefore, may occur during ethanolysis of the *cis*-anhydrides.

The *trans*-configuration of (14), (15) and (16) was also substantiated by their ease of cyclisation with sodium acetate in acetic anhydride to the corresponding 1-acetoxy-naphthalenes (17), (18) and (19), which upon saponification followed by lactonisation of the resulting phenolic acids (20), (21) and (22) gave the corresponding γ -lactones (23), (24) and (25). The appearance of i. r. bands at 780 and 708 cm⁻¹ characteristic of 5-adjacent H atoms, for (24) and (25) proves that ring closure involved the substituted phenyl group. The u. v. spectra of (23), (24) and (25) (cf. Table 4) reflect their naphthalene structure.

Treatment of the anhydrides (11) and (12) with aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene gave a mixture of the corresponding cyclopentenones (26) and (27) and arylidene tetralone carboxylic acids (28 a) and (29 a) respectively. The structure of the cyclopentenones was established by the following evidence: i) They are colourless crystalline products which exclude the possibility of having an oxo-indene structure, ii) the i. r. spectrum of (27) shows bands at 768 and 695 cm⁻¹ (5 adjacent Ar-H), which exclude the possibility of

TABLE 4—LACTONES OF HYDROXYNAPHTHYL ACETIC ACIDS

Compound	M. P. (°C)	Found			Formula	Required%			$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm.}$	ϵ	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$
		C	H	Cl		C	H	Cl			
(23)	159 ⁺	83.4	4.8		C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂	83.1	4.65		242	65070	1799
									288	10030	
(24)	170-1 [‡]	73.2	3.9	11.8	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClO ₂	73.3	3.75	12.0	333*	2700	1799
									249	70370	
(25)	243 [‡]	78.6	4.9		C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	78.6	4.7		395	8480	1792
									335*	2700	
									248	71260	
									290	9630	
									337*	3190	

+from benzene-light petroleum ‡from benzene. Δ of β , γ -unsaturated γ -lactones.^{11(b)}
 *Shoulder

cyclisation on ring (A) and iii) the n.m.r. spectra of (26) and (27) are very similar and show two identical multiplets centred at 7.17τ (2p) and 7.24τ (2p). These are due to second order splitting of $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ protons.^{4,6}

However, the structure of (26) was firmly established by its identity with an authentic specimen of 2,3-diphenyl-cyclopent-2-enone⁵.

The structure of the arylidene tetralone carboxylic acids (28 a) and (29 a) was established by the following evidence: a) the i. r. spectrum of (29 b) lacks $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ of 5-Ar H-atoms, b) they give a D.N.P., and c) the n.m.r. spectrum of (28 b) (cf. experimental).

The *trans*-configuration (Ph/CO₂Et) assigned to the half-esters (4-6) was inferred from their ease of cyclisation with sodium acetate in acetic anhydride to ethyl 4-acetoxy-1-aryl-methyl-2-naphthoates (30), (31) and (32) respectively. These on hydrolysis, methylation and saponification gave the methoxy acids (36 b), (37 b) and (38 b) respectively. Decarboxylation of (36 b) gave 1-benzyl-4-methoxynaphthalene (39),⁶ which supports the structure assigned to these compounds.

Saponification of (5) with alcoholic potassium hydroxide was accompanied by a tautomeric shift of the double bond to give (9) in 89% yield. Syrupy (4) and (6) displayed a similar behaviour as evidenced by the fact that (8) and (10) were obtained in a yield that was significantly higher than expected from mere saponification of (1) and (3) present in the oily fraction (B) of the half-esters (cf. experimental).

An attempt to obtain the pent-3-enoic dibasic acid corresponding to (5) by hydrolysing the latter under milder conditions (aqueous sodium carbonate), led to partial isomerisation, as indicated by the fact that the melting point of the resulting acidic product $142^{\circ}-8^{\circ}$ was raised to $154^{\circ}-8^{\circ}$ upon admixture with (9) (m.p. 170°).

Experimental

Light petroleum refers to the fraction of b.p. $60^{\circ}-80^{\circ}$. I. r. spectra (KBr) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer infracord model 137 and a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer and u.v. spectra (in ethanol) on a Beckman DKI. N.m.r. spectra (in CDCl₃, unless otherwise stated) were determined using a Varian A60 instrument.

p-Methoxybenzyl Phenyl Ketone: This was prepared in 85% yield from *p*-methoxyphenylacetyl chloride (31.0g) and diphenyl cadmium [from bromobenzene (32.1 g), Mg (5.2 g) and cadmium iodide (42.5 g)] by a procedure similar to that used for the synthesis of methyl 4-keto-7-methyloctanoate⁷. The product was purified by distillation, b.p. $180^{\circ}-5^{\circ}/1$ mm. and crystallisation from alcohol to give the ketone, m.p. $96^{\circ}-7^{\circ}$ (lit.⁸ m.p. $94.5^{\circ}-5^{\circ}$) (Found: C, 79.1; H, 6.3. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄O₂, C, 79.6; H, 6.0%). Its D.N.P., deep red needles, m.p. $191^{\circ}-2^{\circ}$ (from acetone) (Found: C, 62.2; H, 4.8; N, 13.65. C₂₁H₁₈N₄O₅ requires C, 62.1; H, 4.5; N, 13.8%).

Condensation of Benzyl-, p-Chloro- and p-Methoxybenzyl-Phenyl Ketones with Diethyl Succinate: A solution of the ketone (1 mol) in diethyl succinate (1.5 mol) was added dropwise to a boiling stirred solution of potassium *t*-butoxide [from potassium (1.2 g atom)] in

excess of *t*-butanol during 30 min, after which stirring and boiling were continued for a further 90 min. and worked up as usual.¹ Upon extraction of the ethereal solution of the condensation product of the first two ketones with cold concentrated sodium carbonate solution, a sodium salt crystallised out (fraction A) in the alkaline layer. This was filtered off and acidified. The oil which solidified on standing was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum to give *cis* (Ph/Ar)-5-aryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoic acids (1) and (2), respectively.

The alkaline filtrate precipitated on acidification an oily half-esters (fraction B), which failed to solidify in the case of benzylphenyl ketone and was partially crystallised (benzene-light petroleum) in the case of *p*-chlorobenzyl phenyl ketone to give *trans* (Ph/CO₂Et)-5-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-phenyl-pent-3-enoic acid (5).

However, in the case of *p*-methoxybenzyl phenyl ketone the alkaline solution was acidified and the precipitated oil extracted with ether. The oily product solidified on trituration with benzene-light petroleum (fraction A). Evaporation of the mother liquor left an oil (fraction B), from which few crystals came down on standing. The results are reported in Table 1,

The n.m.r. spectrum of (1) shows a multiplet at $2.5-3.0\tau$ (10 p) (aromatic), and unsymmetrical singlet at 3.3τ (1 p) (olefinic), and two multiplets centred at 6.03τ (1 p) ($-\text{CH}-$) and 7.15τ (2 p) ($-\text{CH}_2-$), split by second order coupling^{4,6} probably due to partial restriction of rotation, of the CH₂COOH group, around the CH-CH₂-bond, and thus the CH₂ protons will not be equally deshielded, as well as to weak coupling of the CH-proton with the olefinic proton. The spectrum also shows a singlet at 6.2τ (3 p) for the OCH₃ group.

Establishment of the Structure of the Isomeric Half-esters and Estimation of their Ratios in the Reaction Product: This was accomplished by bubbling ozonized oxygen in a cold chloroform solution (30:1) of the half-ester (10 g) for 60 min. The ozonide was decomposed with zinc dust (0.3 g) and 5% aqueous acetic acid (15 ml) (1/2 hr reflux). The product was extracted with chloroform and worked up according to any of the following two procedures: (i) In the case of the solid *cis* half-esters (1), (2) and (3), the chloroform solution was extracted with a saturated solution of sodium carbonate from which β -benzoylpropionic acid (m.p. and mixed m.p. 117°) was recovered by acidification. The chloroform mother liquor was evaporated in a stream of CO₂ and the remaining aldehyde was identified and estimated as its D.N.P. The weights of the acid and aldehyde accounted for ca. 93% recovery. (ii) In the case of the oily fractions of half-esters (B), the chloroform solution after being extracted with sodium carbonate, was evaporated and the residue heated with reflux for 4 hr with hydrogen peroxide (100 v) (20 ml) to oxidise any aldehyde to the benzoic acid. The product was extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution to remove the benzoic acid and the ether removed to leave the arylmethyl phenyl ketone.

From the amount of the β -benzoylpropionic acid and the arylmethyl phenyl ketone the ratios of the two

isomeric half-esters in oily fractions were calculated based on ca. 93% recovery. The results are reported in Table 2.

Ozonolysis of the dibasic acids (8), (9) and (10) (inter alia) by procedure (i) gave β -benzoylpropionic acid together with the corresponding aromatic aldehyde.

Estimation of the Ratios of the Isomeric Half-esters (2) and (5) in the Oily Half-ester Fractions (B) by u.v. spectroscopy: Values for E_{obs}/E_1 were plotted versus the values for E_2/E_1 where E_{obs} is the optical density of (B), E_1 and E_2 are the optical densities of the half-esters (2) and (5), respectively, at the same wavelengths. A straight line was obtained from which the ratios of (2) and (5) were calculated to be 1.1:1, respectively.³

The validity of the method was established by its application to a mixture of known concentrations of (2) and (5).

The Dibasic Acids (8), (9) and (10): The half-esters (1), (2) and (3) were hydrolysed with 5% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10 ml) as usual⁹ to give *cis* (Ph/Ar)-5-aryl-3-carboxy-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoic acids (cf. Table 3). The n.m.r. spectrum of (8) shows a singlet at 3.2 τ (1 p) (olefinic), two multiplets at 5.9-6.1 τ (1 p) and at 6.9-7.5 τ (2 p) which stand for the CH and CH₂ protons (split by second order coupling), respectively.

The Isomeric Half-esters (14), (15) and (16): The dibasic acids (8), (9) and (10) (1.0 g) were converted by refluxing with acetyl chloride (13 ml) for 2 hr into the corresponding syrupy anhydrides (11), (12) and (13), which were then refluxed with absolute ethanol (4 ml) for 4 hr. Evaporation of the alcohol gave *ethyl trans* (Ph/Ar)-5-aryl-3-carboxy-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoates (14) (0.96 g), had m. p. 112° (from benzene-light petroleum). (Found: C, 73.9; H, 6.3%). (15) and (16), however, were obtained as viscous oils which failed to solidify.

The n.m.r. spectrum of (14) shows a signal at 2.63-2.85 τ (10 p) (aromatic), a singlet at 3.22 τ (1 p) (olefinic), a multiplet at 5.8-6.05 τ (1 p) (-CH-), a singlet at 6.3 τ (3 p) (OCH₃) and a multiplet at 7.05-7.3 τ (2 p) (-CH₂-). The splitting of the signals for the CH and CH₂ are probably due to the same reason mentioned for (1).

Saponification of the Anhydride (11): This was achieved by treating the anhydride (1.0 g) with 1% sodium hydrogen carbonate (30 ml) at room temperature for 6 hrs. Acidification and extraction with ether followed by evaporation of the dried ethereal solution gave the *cis*-dibasic acid (8) (0.85 g), m. p. and mixed m. p. 151°.

Cyclisation of the Isomeric Half-esters (14), (15) and (16): These (1 g) were heated with sodium acetate (0.4 g), a trace of zinc chloride and acetic anhydride (6 ml) under reflux for 4 hr and worked up as usual⁹ to give the corresponding 1-acetoxy-naphthalenes (17), (18) and (19). (18) 0.72 g had m. p. 131°-2° (from light petroleum). (Found: C, 69.3; H, 5.05; Cl, 9.3. C₂₂H₁₉ClO₄ requires C, 69.0; H, 5.0; Cl, 9.3%) ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ at 1735 and 1770 cm⁻¹). However, (17) and (19) were obtained as viscous oils which failed to solidify.

1',2' (3'-Phenylnaphtho) (c)-2,3-dihydrofuran-2-one (23), 1',2' (7'-chloro-3'-phenylnaphtho) (c)-2,3-dihydrofuran-2-one (24) and 1',2' (7'-methoxy-3'-phenylnaphtho) (c)-2,3-dihydrofuran-2-one (25): The ethyl acetoxynaphthyl acetates (17), (18) and (19) were saponified as usual to give the corresponding hydroxynaphthyl acetic acids (20), (21) and (22) in ca. 90% yield, as brownish syrups which solidified on trituration with benzene-light petroleum but could not be obtained in a crystalline form. They were directly lactonised to (23), (24) and (25), respectively, by refluxing with dry benzene for 4 hrs and crystallising from a suitable solvent (cf. Table 4).

In the u.v. spectra the red shift in the ¹B_u and ¹L_b bands compared with those of naphthalene is caused by auxochromic substituents in the β -position.

Action of Anhydrous Aluminium Chloride on cis Pent-4-enoic Anhydrides (11) and (12): The anhydride (8.5 g) was treated with aluminium chloride (6.5 g) in nitrobenzene (75 ml) and worked up as usual.⁹ The residue after steam distillation was extracted with aqueous sodium carbonate. The neutral products 2,3-diphenylcyclopent-2-enone (26) and 2-p-chlorophenyl-3-phenylcyclopent-2-enone (27) were crystallised from *n*-hexane (cf. Table 5). Their n.m.r. spectra (DMSO) show multiplets at 2.5-2.8 τ and 2.7-2.85 τ , respectively, for aromatic protons, and two identical multiplets centred at 7.17 τ and 7.24 τ for the -CH₂-CH₂-grouping. The ratios of the aliphatic to aromatic protons in the n.m.r. spectra of (26) and (27) are 4:10 and 4:9, respectively.

In the u.v. spectra the long wavelength band (293 nm) appears to be due to excitation in the two conjugated aryl groups (cf. *cis*-stilbene),¹⁰ whereas, the short wavelength band (266 and 228 nm, respectively) is more likely due to excitation in the α,β -unsaturated system.

Acidification of the carbonate solution gave syrupy acids, which were directly converted into their methyl esters (CH₃OH and HCl gas) and crystallised from methanol (cf. Table 5).

The n.m.r. spectrum of (28 b) shows a peak at 2.5-2.7 τ (9 p) (aromatic), a sharp singlet at 3.07 τ (1 p) (olefinic), a distorted triplet centred at 6.07 τ (1 p) (proton b), a sharp singlet at 6.37 τ (3 p) (CH₃ of aliphatic esters), and a quartet of equal intensity centred at 6.67 τ (2 p) (proton c). The complex spectrum of the CH₂ in the -CO. CH₂-CH-group, which deviates from a true A₂X system is probably due to the non-equivalence of the two CH₂ protons due to the non-symmetry of the molecule, since one of these protons lies *cis* and the other *trans* to the CO₂Me.

Cyclisation of the Oily Half-ester Fractions (B): These were cyclised with sodium acetate, zinc chloride and acetic anhydride as usual⁹ to give *ethyl 4-acetoxy-1-arylmethyl-2-naphthoates* (30), (31) and (32), which with the exception of (32) were viscous oils. (32) had m. p. 102° (from ethanol) (Found: C, 69.0; H, 5.2; Cl, 9.0. C₂₂H₁₉ClO₄ requires C, 69.0; H, 5.0; Cl 9.3%). $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ at 1730 and 1770 cm⁻¹.

Saponification of the above acetoxynaphthoates with 5% sodium hydroxide gave the 1-arylmethyl-4-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids (33), (34) and (35), which were

TABLE 5—ISOMERISATION PRODUCTS OF CIS(PH/AR)-5-ARYL-3-CARBOXY-4-PHENYLPENT-4-ENOIC ANHYDRIDES

Compound	Yield %	M. P. (°C)	Found			Formula	Required%			λmax/ nm.	ε	ν C=O/cm ⁻¹
			C	H	Cl		C	H	Cl			
(26)	63.5	94 ^Δ	87.5	5.7	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O	87.1	6.0	—	266 292	17730 13510	1718 ^x
(27)	65	87	76.5	5.2	12.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClO	76.0	4.9	13.2	228 293	24310 16380	1718 ^x
(28 b) ⁺	31	122-3	77.6	5.3	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃	78.1	5.5	—	218 266 330*	47100 14180 6140	1688 ^{xx} 1735 ^{xxx}
(29 b)††	32	134	69.4	5.1	—	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClO ₃	69.8	4.6	10.9	221 280 330*	41890 17080 8910	1692 ^{xx} 1742 ^{xxx}

⁺Its D. N. P. had m. p. 20° (from ethyl acetate) (Found : N. 12.0. C₂₅H₁₉N₄O₆ requires : N. 11.9%).

††Its D. N. P. had m. p. 244° (from ethyl acetate) (Found : N. 11.3. C₂₅H₁₈ClN₄O₆ requires : N. 11.05%).

x of 5-membered α,β-unsaturated ketones.11(c) *Shoulder, x x of aryl ketones.11(c). ΔLit,⁵m,p, 95-6.
x x x of aliphatic esters.11(b)

TABLE 6—1-ARYLMETHYL-4-HYDROXY-2-NAPHTHOIC ACIDS AND ESTERS

Compound	M. P. °C	Found			Formula	Required %			νOH/x cm ⁻¹	ν C=O ^{xx} cm ⁻¹	λmax/ nm	
		C	H	Cl		C	H	Cl				
(33)	211 ⁺	77.45	5.0	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₃	77.7	5.1	—	3420	1685		
(34)	220 ^Δ	68.8	4.0	10.8	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClO ₃	69.1	4.2	11.3	3520	1705		
(35)	235 ^{ΔΔ}	74.4	5.6	—	C ₁ H ₁₆ O ₄	74.0	5.2	—	3585	1692		
(36a)	132 [‡]	78.7	5.4	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃	78.4	5.9	—	—	1710		
(37a)	156 [‡]	70.8	5.2	10.1	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ ClO ₃	70.5	5.0	10.4	—	1718		
(36b)	226 [‡]	77.9	6.0	—	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃	78.1	5.5	—	—	1680	271.5 244 301 270 ^x 327 218 242 301 279 ^x	53470 44870 7950 3470 4010 71290 54760 10100 6530
(37b)	223 [‡]	70.2	4.6	10.9	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClO ₃	69.8	4.6	10.85	—	1695	216 242.5 287 302	51170 43170 7450 7750
(38b)	193 [‡]	74.2	5.9	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄	74.5	5.6	—	—	1690		

‡ from ethanol
+ from toluene
xx of aryl acids^{11a}

‡ from benzene
Δ from ether

x Shoulder
ΔΔ from ether-benzene
x phenolic OH^{11d}

methylated with diazomethane in ether (50 ml) to the corresponding methoxynaphthoates (36 a), (37 a) and (38 a); the latter failed to solidify (cf. Table 6).

The methoxynaphthoates (1.0 g) were saponified with 5% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10 ml) to the *methoxynaphthoic acids* (36 b), (37 b) and (38 b) (0.9 g) (cf. Table 6).

1-Benzyl-4-methoxynaphthalene (39) : The methoxy acid (36 b) (0.5 g) was heated with copper bronze (0.5 g) in boiling quinoline (5 ml) for 3 hr and worked up as usual⁹ to give the title compound (39) (0.3 g), m.p. 85-6° (from ethanol), undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen⁶.

Isomerization of trans (Ph/CO₂Et)-5-p-Chlorophenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-phenyl-pent-3-enoic Acid (5) to cis (Ph/Ar)-3-Carboxy-5-p-Chlorophenyl-4-phenyl-pent-4-enoic Acid (9) : When (5) (1.5 g) was saponified by refluxing with 5% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (15 ml) for 2 hr it gave a *dibasic acid* (1.3 g, 89%) which was crystallised from toluene-light petroleum to give (9), m.p. 170°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen. Similar treatment of the oily half-esters (4) and (6) gave rise to pure *cis-dibasic acids* (8) and (10), respectively.

However, when (5) (1.0 g) was saponified by refluxing with 10% aqueous sodium carbonate (10 ml) for 1 hr, the resulting acidic product (0.7 g) after several crystallisation from toluene-light petroleum had m.p. 142-8°, raised to 154-8° on admixture with (9).

(4) Ar = Ph

(5) Ar = p-Cl.C₆H₄.

(6) Ar = p-MeO.C₆H₄.

(30) Ar = Ph.

(31) Ar = p-Cl.C₆H₄

(32) Ar = p-MeO.C₆H₄

(33) Ar = Ph, R¹ = H, R² = CO₂H

(34) Ar = p-Cl.C₆H₄, R¹ = H, R² = CO₂H

(35) Ar = p-MeO.C₆H₄, R¹ = H, R² = CO₂H

(36a) Ar = Ph, R¹ = Me, R² = CO₂Me

b) Ar = Ph, R¹ = Me, R² = CO₂H

(37a) Ar = p-Cl.C₆H₄, R¹ = Me, R² = CO₂Me

b) Ar = p-Cl.C₆H₄, R¹ = Me, R² = CO₂H

(38a) Ar = p-MeO.C₆H₄, R¹ = Me, R² = CO₂Me

b) Ar = p-MeO.C₆H₄, R¹ = Me, R² = CO₂H

(39) Ar = Ph, R¹ = Me, R² = H

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